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Instructional supervision on teaching practices, performance and learning outcomes

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Abstract

This study determined the relationship between instructional supervision and teachers' teaching practices and performance and the learning outcomes of the students in selected high schools in EDDIS III, Bulacan during the School Year 2019-2020. With 346 teachers as respondents of the study, findings showed that the respondents always conducted instructional supervision in their respective schools. Likewise, respondents always utilized teaching practices such as differentiated instruction and cooperative learning. In the same manner, respondents always showed outstanding teaching performance. Meanwhile, the learning outcomes of the students were described as very satisfactory. Highly significant correlations were found between instructional supervision and teaching practices and the performance of teacher respondents. Similarly, a highly significant correlation was found between instructional supervision and the learning outcomes of the students. Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: There is a significant relationship between instructional supervision and teaching practices. There is a significant relationship between instructional supervision and teaching performance. There is a significant relationship between instructional supervision and learning outcomes.

Keywords: Instructional Supervision; Teaching Performance; Teaching Practices; Learning Outcomes

1. Introduction

Instructional supervision is one of the many ways to ensure that the schools' mission, vision, and goal are being implemented through empowering, equipping, and enhancing teachers' skills with the help of observation to provide meaningful learning for students. In our present situation, teachers are undergoing instructional supervision thru the classroom observation tool. Moreover, school managers observe teachers in an actual teaching scenario and provide post-observation after the actual teaching observation. Thus, teachers may benefit from the feedback given by the instructional supervisor that can lead to student growth and development.

In addition, training, seminar-workshop, and learning action cell sessions were provided to cater to the needs of both teachers and the students which may result in an increase in the learning outcomes and teacher's performance.

The Northern Bedford County School District (2008) provides a system of differentiated supervision such as direct supervision, mentoring, administrative mentoring, peer coaching, self-directed supervision, instructional leadership, professional colloquium, action research, and national teacher certification [1].

In addition to the above mentioned, the principals' main role is to orient the new teaching staff, supervise curriculum, timetabling, and monitor students' academic progress. Hence, a principal should be setting time for instructional supervision in schools because it influences the students' academic achievement positively. (Samoie, 2014) [2].

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Sergiovanni and Starrat (as cited in Mwaniki & Guantai, 2018), note that teacher instructional supervision plays a powerful role in developing and nurturing the educational competencies of a teacher, which in turn contributes to the academic success of the students [3]. In addition, classroom observation has the biggest role in instructional supervision which can help a teacher grow in different aspects with the aid of different observation tools. It may be done formally or informally depending on the needs and wants of the immediate superior. Thus, the observer must have to prioritize the proper approach in order to improve the quality of teaching as well as the preparation of learning episodes.

Having frequent classroom observation may help teachers enhance their knowledge of the effective classroom strategies that will cater to the needs of every student. Through the given feedback, it will help improve the quality of instruction. Moreover, Abubakr (2015) stated that continuous supervisory training for teachers and teachers can create an enabling environment in which roles are appreciated in the development of teaching practices to improve professional development [4].

According to the Reform Support Network (2015), several challenges that prevent observers from providing meaningful feedback is by using observation rubrics with a lack of specificity [5]. Thus, observers find it hard to assess teachers' performance if there are unclear expectations for teacher practice or assessing too many indicators at once.

Many reasons have arisen why some of the teachers, even observers find classroom observation ineffective, bias and unreliable. According to Dynarski (2015), teacher evaluation systems need a stronger scientific basis to understand effective teaching and to measure teachers' effectiveness [6]. Moreover, more research is needed to identify teaching practices rather than using notions of what effective teachers should be doing.

Evaluation systems that tell us what effective teachers should be doing are not clear and misleading. In addition, solid research about what aspects of teaching improve learning is much needed.

In line with this, the Department of Education, through the Teacher Education Council issues DepEd Order no. 42, S.2017 entitled "National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers" [7].

It contains 7 Domains which collectively comprise 37 strands that refer to more specific dimensions of teacher practices. All performance appraisal for teachers shall be based on this set of standards. Furthermore, it also aims to apply a uniform measure to assess teachers' performance, identify needs, and provide support for professional development. It has a supervisory tool known as the Classroom Observation Tool (COT) which is useful to collect information from the actual teaching-learning activity in the classroom base on the domains. This observation tool is aligned with Philippine Professional Standard for Teachers. Hence, teachers need to develop their 21st-century skills to get along with 21st-century learners. Thus, observation might be of great help to improve those skills.

It is important that the analysis is as unbiased as expected and that advisors are aware of their own preferences and predispositions so that the data obtained is as valid and reliable as possible and not intended to validate a point.

According to Will (2020), observations in the classroom are another main component of an evaluation. But things look different now, teachers are struggling to adjust to a modern environment of distance learning, and with student access, there are significant inequities [8].

Based on the aforementioned discussions of related literature, the researcher formulated the following research problem and research questions. Moreover, this study was conducted to find out how instructional supervision through COT affects teaching practices and performance as well as the learning outcomes.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Research Design

This study used the explanatory sequential mixed-methods of research in which quantitative and qualitative approaches are mixed in a single study. The design of this proposed study is descriptive research. The use of the descriptive method of research was preferred by the researcher for both qualitative and quantitative data collection and analysis emphasizing the relationship between instructional supervision and teaching performance, teaching practices, and learning outcomes

For the qualitative part, teacher-informants were interviewed online regarding their perception of the implementation of the classroom observation tool. Most significant stories of teachers about their experiences during a classroom observation. Supporting numerical data from a survey questionnaire through google forms were also used to enrich and substantiate the qualitative data.

2.2. Data Gathering Techniques

Prior to the gathering of the data, the researcher sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent in Bulacan in collecting the required data. She wrote a request letter addressed to the superintendent and asked help from the schools' administrative staff to submit it to the division office. Upon permitted, the researcher also secured permits from the school heads where the study was conducted.

After permission was granted, the researcher proceeded to the concerned respondents and informants to conduct the usual procedure of the distribution of research instruments up to the retrieval. The instrument was administered online through google forms at the appointed date to the secondary schools in San Rafael. In order to obtain the correct and accurate information, the respondents and informants were briefed and oriented on the purpose of the study. It is estimated that one hundred percent of the instrument was retrieved and that it was fully completed.

The interview guide questions were the main instrument in gathering the needed data for the study. The questionnaire was adapted from the different instruments such as Individual Performance and Commitment Rating Tool and Classroom Observation Tool and was composed of three parts.

Part I of the questionnaire provided significant information about the instructional supervision done by the school head to his/her teachers in terms of classroom observation.

The part II of the questionnaire provided insight of the teachers regarding their experiences encountered during observation and the impact of classroom observation on the teaching practices, performance, and learning outcomes.

Moreover, part III is the qualitative data of the study wherein sets of guide questions were given to get the courses of action to enhance the capabilities in dealing with observations, improve classroom instruction, and their perception of the instructional supervisory tool. This study gathered information about the impact of revised classroom tools on teaching practices, performance, and learning outcomes.

2.3. Sampling Procedure

The researcher used the total enumeration in the conduct of the study in teacher-informants. The researcher got 346 teacher-informants among the five secondary schools in San Rafael, Bulacan. 175 from Carlos F. Gonzales High School, 35 from Salapungan National High School, 74 from San Rafael National Trade School, 34 from Maronquillo High School, and 28 from Lydia Villangca Trade School.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Instructional Supervision

Instructional supervision is a professional continuous and cooperative process for the improvement of instruction. It is characterized by guidance, assistance, sharing of ideas, facilitation, or creation to help teachers improve learning situations and quality of learning in the schools.

3.1.1. Planning

Table 1 The Instructional Supervision in terms of Planning

Item Statement	Responses (N=346)					Mean	VD
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. Orients new teaching staff.	209	95	27	15	0	4.44	A
2. Develops and promotes innovative and effective teaching-learning, approaches, strategies, and techniques.	195	115	27	9	0	4.43	A

3. Implements innovative and alternative delivery schemes in teaching and learning.	191	123	22	10	0	4.43	A
4. Implements, monitors, supervise, and assess the school curriculum to assure higher learning outcomes.	202	110	23	11	0	4.45	A
5. Localizes/indigenizes curriculum.	155	142	37	11	1	4.27	A
6. Proposes innovations to improve instruction.	195	111	28	11	1	4.41	A
Overall Mean						4.41	A

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description
4.21 – 5.00	Always (A)
3.41 – 4.20	Often (O)
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes (S)
1.81 – 2.60	Rarely (R)
1.00 – 1.80	Never (N)

Table 1 presents the perceptions of the teachers with regard to instructional supervision in terms of planning. It can be noted from the table that all items indicated therein garnered the highest verbal description of “always”. A closer look at the table shows that the item “Implements, monitors, supervise, and assess the school curriculum to assure higher learning outcomes” got the highest computed weighted mean of 4.45. Meanwhile, item “Localizes/indigenizes curriculum” received the lowest computed weighted mean of 4.27. The overall was recorded at 4.41.

These results imply that curriculum and instruction are the meat of the educational process. Real change in education comes with changes in the content that teachers teach, and students learn, and in the instructional methods that teachers use. Both curriculum and instruction in turn are shaped by expectations about the kinds of educational outcomes that students should manifest by the time they graduate from high school.

Accordingly, Akwesi (2018) asserted that curriculum implementation is the practical application of theory into practice in a way that the eventual outcome is evidenced through the learners’ performances in and outside the classroom. When teachers deliver both the curriculum contents and instructional strategies in the way and manner they were designed to be delivered, curriculum implementation is said to have occurred [9]. However, the ability and effectiveness of the teacher to carry out curriculum implementation depend to large extent on some variables like knowledge/experience qualification, availability of resources, and motivational issues among others.

The findings of the interview supported the results of the study. In the conducted interview, teacher respondents were asked “Is there a difference between your preparation for a usual classroom teaching and your preparation for instructional supervision.” Respondents answered that they prepared for the lessons every day even without scheduled observation. However, they stated that when the observation is announced, they prepared more as compared to their daily activities in class. Further, they stated that planning is very important in every class. They also added that when everything is planned, the class will run very smoothly.

3.1.2. Monitoring

Table 2 The Instructional Supervision in terms of Monitoring

Item Statement	Responses (N=346)					Mean	VD
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. Assumes leadership and supervises teachers on the improvement of instructional programs specifically the teaching-learning process.	193	105	40	8	0	4.40	A
2. Motivates and supports teachers to attain peak performance.	200	105	37	4	0	4.45	A
3. Assists teachers in identifying strengths and growth areas through monitoring and evaluation.	185	115	38	8	0	4.38	A
4. Provides professional, technical, and instructional assistance to teachers and school heads.	191	106	44	5	0	4.40	A
5. Promotes DepEd programs and projects to improve teaching and learning.	197	113	32	4	0	4.45	A

6. Promotes the efficiency of teaching and learning in all classes through observation and visitations.	193	110	34	9	0	4.41	A
7. Evaluates the performance of teachers.	193	109	34	8	2	4.40	A
Overall Mean						4.41	A

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description
4.21 – 5.00	Always (A)
3.41 – 4.20	Often (O)
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes (S)
1.81 – 2.60	Rarely (R)
1.00 – 1.80	Never (N)

Table 2 displays the perceptions of the teachers as regards instructional supervision in terms of monitoring. It can be seen from the table that all items indicated therein including the computed overall mean of 4.41 obtained the highest verbal interpretation of “always”. Further examination of the same table reveals that items “Motivates and supports teachers to attain peak performance” and “Promotes DepEd programs and projects to improve teaching and learning” registered the highest computed weighted mean of 4.45. On the other hand, the item “Assists teachers in identifying strengths and growth areas through monitoring and evaluation” received the lowest computed weighted mean of 4.38.

These findings imply that by having good work motivation in performing duties and responsibilities, a teacher will be able to lift and push the spirit to continue to complete the work. In addition to teachers’ motivation, there are some external factors that can support their performance including the leadership of the principal in conducting direction, guidance, and provision of care that is done continuously and sustainably.

In the same vein, Abdul Hads and Nurhayati (2015) reported that supervision is the assistance in terms of motivation given to subordinates (teachers) to grow both personally and socially with an emphasis on professional aspects [10]. Thus, it can be interpreted that supervision is a systematic and well-planned effort undertaken by a school administrator to foster, encourage, motivate, and direct the teachers to achieve educational goals effectively through a better learning process.

Results of the conducted interview corroborate with the quantitative findings of the study. When the teacher respondents were asked if they experienced instructional supervision, all of them replied “yes”. Further, they added that they firmly believed that instructional supervision provides them guidance and helps them to enhance their teaching practices that ultimately improve their students’ academic performance.

Teacher respondents were also asked, “What do you usually feel whenever you are experiencing instructional supervision?” They answered that they felt nervous at the beginning of the observation but as the class goes on they already felt at ease and comfortable.

In the conducted interview with the school heads and supervisor, they were asked “How often do you visit classrooms to observe teachers teaching?” They answered, once every quarter or as the need arises. Furthermore, they were also asked, “Would you explain the instructional supervisory roles you have found effective?” They responded to classroom observation as can easily be addressed the needs of both teachers and the students.

3.1.3. Feedback

Table 3 exhibits the perceptions of the teachers regarding instructional supervision in terms of feedback.

It can be examined from the table that all items reflected therein including the registered overall mean of 4.37 obtained the highest verbal interpretation of “always”. Further examination of the tabulated results shows that item “Conducts learning action cell (LAC) sessions to cater the needs of every teacher” received the highest computed weighted mean of 4.49. Meanwhile, the item “Initiates action research designed to improve instruction and academic performance” obtained the lowest computed weighted mean of 4.24.

Table 3 The Instructional Supervision in terms of Feedback

Item Statement	Responses (N=346)					Mean	VD
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. Conducts post-conference after the classroom observation for future improvement.	201	92	45	5	3	4.40	A
2. Conducts seminars, workshops and other service training programs.	204	94	43	2	3	4.43	A
3. Initiates action research designed to improve instruction and academic performance.	165	116	52	10	3	4.24	A
4. Conducts learning action cell (LAC) sessions to cater the needs of every teachers.	224	77	38	4	3	4.49	A
5. Serves as consultant in the in-service trainings.	169	118	46	12	1	4.28	A
Overall Mean						4.37	A

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description
4.21 – 5.00	Always (A)
3.41 – 4.20	Often (O)
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes (S)
1.81 – 2.60	Rarely (R)
1.00 – 1.80	Never (N)

These findings imply that when providing feedback on a colleague's teaching performance, it is important to remember that the principal's role is not to judge or evaluate a teacher's approach to teaching or teaching style, or to demonstrate everything that he/she might know about teaching. Rather, the goal is to share strategies and perspectives through learning action cells that will help the teacher identify a plan for improving her or his teaching practice. As observers, principals are reflecting back to the teacher what it is like to be a student learning in his or her class.

In conjunction with the present findings, Willems (2018) asserted that observation and feedback is a process that is vitally important to the educational environment and it is essential that there is a symbiotic relationship between the two [11]. Teachers observe their students on an ongoing basis and provide feedback according to the success, or otherwise, of learning activities in the classroom. Students observe their teachers on an ongoing basis, while feedback is provided in terms of their response to instructions and effective completion of tasks. Teachers, in turn, are observed by school administrators, whose job it is to evaluate their effectiveness, both for reasons of accountability, and provide recorded feedback on pedagogic practice in the classroom for either summative or formative purposes. If applied well, observation and feedback can encourage continuing professional development (CPD) and provide support and training, however, if the reverse is true they can lead to careers lost and significant issues with self-belief.

In the conducted interview with the teacher respondents, they were asked "Do you find instructional supervision helpful in your development as a teacher?" these respondents replied that they strongly believed that instructional supervision is very helpful for them to know their strengths and weaknesses in teaching. Moreover, they added that instructional supervision made them aware of the things that they need to improve to make their teaching more effective.

In addition to the above mentioned, in the conducted interview with the school heads and supervisor, they were asked "In your opinion, do you think that these supervisory roles can contribute to the improvement of the teaching practices, performance, and learning outcomes?" They all answered "yes". Furthermore, they added that instructional supervision can help teachers improve their strategies and skills. Also, supervisory roles can easily identify the strength and areas that need improvement. However, as they were asked "How would instructional supervision be improved in your division/department/school?" They answered, it will improve through attending seminar workshops and evaluating teachers' performance as the basis for the next instructional supervision. Whereas, ineffective practices such as too much workload needs to be eliminated.

3.1.4. Assessment

Table 4 The Instructional Supervision in terms of Assessment

Item Statement	Responses (N=346)					Mean	VD
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. Undertakes periodic evaluation of learner's achievement as basis for INSET and curriculum adaptation.	202	110	23	11	0	4.45	A
2. Assists, ensures utilization of a range of assessment processes of learners performance.	165	116	52	10	3	4.24	A
3. Leads in the evaluation of learner's achievement and utilizes results to improve learning.	202	110	23	11	0	4.45	A
4. Evaluates learning outcomes vis – a –vis the curriculum.	202	110	23	11	0	4.45	A
5. Develops, promotes innovative and effective assessment approaches, strategies and techniques.	195	115	27	9	0	4.43	A
6. Assists teachers in identifying strengths and growth areas through monitoring and observation.	185	115	38	8	0	4.38	A
Overall Mean						4.40	A

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description
4.21 – 5.00	Always (A)
3.41 – 4.20	Often (O)
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes (S)
1.81 – 2.60	Rarely (R)
1.00 – 1.80	Never (N)

Table 4 summarizes the perceptions of the teachers about instructional supervision in terms of assessment. It can be observed from the table that all items indicated therein, including the overall mean of 4.40 received the highest verbal description of "always". Further observation of the table reveals that items "Undertakes periodic evaluation of learner's achievement as a basis for INSET and curriculum adaptation", "Leads in the evaluation of learner's achievement and utilizes results to improve learning", and "Evaluates learning outcomes vis – a –vis the curriculum" yielded the highest computed weighted mean of 4.45. On the other hand, item "Assists, ensures utilization of a range of assessment processes of learners performance" obtained the lowest computed weighted mean of 4.24. These results imply that the primary purpose of assessment and evaluation is to improve student learning. Information gathered through assessment and evaluations helps teachers to identify students' difficulties as well as to detect weaknesses in programs. Results also showed that respondents were aware that assessment and evaluations are important tools for adapting curriculum and instructional approaches to students' needs and for determining the overall effectiveness of programs and classroom practices.

Accordingly, Spencer (2017) reiterated that assessment and evaluation strategies are based on the provincial curriculum expectations and on the achievement level descriptions and categories in the achievement chart [12]. Assessment and evaluation strategies are varied in nature, administered over a period of time, and designed to provide opportunities for students to demonstrate the full range of their learning. In addition, teachers will use both their professional judgment and student observations in evaluating specific criteria and achievement.

Moreover, Sewagegn (2019) stated that the importance of assessment in assessing the standard of education cannot be overstated [13]. This is especially true when students are adequately evaluated using a variety of effective evaluation methods.

3.2. Teaching Practices

Teachers' practices are important for understanding and improving educational processes. They are closely linked to teachers' strategies for coping with challenges in their daily professional life and to their general well-being, and they shape students' learning environment and influence student motivation and achievement.

3.2.1. Differentiated Instruction

Table 5 The Teaching Practices in terms of Differentiated Instruction

Item Statement	Responses (N=346)					Mean	VD
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. Uses differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learners' gender, needs, strength, interest, and experiences.	187	124	30	4	1	4.42	A
2. Vary the complexity along the lines of concrete, symbolic or abstract explorations.	124	175	39	7	1	4.20	O
3. Vary the resources, involving narrative, informational, multimedia, experts and guests.	143	155	39	8	1	4.25	A
4. Vary the context from classrooms, programs, communities, and virtual environment.	141	161	34	9	1	4.25	A
5. Arranges flexible groupings and peer activities.	169	135	33	8	1	4.34	A
6. Provide roles and clear expectations for group members.	172	141	28	4	1	4.38	A
7. Uses problem-based learning, service learning and performance-based experiences.	156	145	38	7	0	4.30	A
8. Expecting student work that reflects multiple intelligences.	167	137	36	5	1	4.34	A
Overall Mean						4.31	A

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description
4.21 – 5.00	Always (A)
3.41 – 4.20	Often (O)
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes (S)
1.81 – 2.60	Rarely (R)
1.00 – 1.80	Never (N)

Table 5 reveals the perceptions of the respondents as regards their teaching practices in terms of differentiated instruction.

It can be gleaned from the table that item "Uses differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learners' gender, needs, strength, interest and experiences" received the highest computed weighted mean of 4.42 with a verbal description of "always". On the other hand, item "Vary the complexity along the lines of concrete, symbolic or abstract explorations" yielded the lowest computed weighted mean of 4.20 with a verbal description of "often". The overall mean was recorded at 4.31 which is verbally interpreted as "always".

These results imply that respondents utilized teaching strategies wherein students can demonstrate varying learning abilities, academic levels, learning styles, and learning preferences. Further, these strategies are appropriate for their needs and tailored to meet their unique needs.

In conjunction with the present findings, in differentiating instruction, teachers proactively modify the curriculum, teaching methods, resources, learning activities, and student products to address the needs of individual students and small groups of students to maximize the learning opportunity for each student in the classroom.

3.2.2. Integrated Technology

Table 6 The Teaching Practices in terms of Integrated Technology

Item Statement	Responses (N=346)					Mean	VD
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. Selects, develops, organizes, and uses appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals.	174	132	33	5	2	4.36	A
2. Incorporates technology-based lessons such as audio-video presentations.	138	161	38	8	1	4.23	A
3. Encourages students to use graphics, audio or video in completing their task.	132	146	57	9	2	4.15	O
4. Encourages students to use a word processing application to write, edit and print their requirements.	117	155	60	12	2	4.08	O
5. Incorporates online news stories into the curriculum.	119	136	77	11	3	4.03	O
Overall Mean						4.17	O

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description
4.21 – 5.00	Always (A)
3.41 – 4.20	Often (O)
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes (S)
1.81 – 2.60	Rarely (R)
1.00 – 1.80	Never (N)

Table 6 shows the perceptions of the respondents about their teaching practices in terms of integrated technology.

It can be observed from the table that the item “Selects, develops, organizes, and uses appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals” obtained the highest computed weighted mean of 4.36 which is verbally described as “always”. On the other hand, item “Incorporates online news stories into the curriculum” received the lowest computed weighted mean of 4.03 which is verbally interpreted as “often”. The overall mean was registered at 4.17 with a verbal interpretation of “often”.

These results imply that respondents strongly believed that ICTs can empower teachers and learners, making significant contributions to learning and achievement. Moreover, they felt that introduction and use of ICT adequately will be extremely effective in students’ learning and achievement.

Studies by Macho (2015), Ghavifekr and Rosdy (2015), and a number of other researchers have confirmed that the use of ICT in education would help enhance students’ learning [14][15]. Previous researchers have shown that teaching with the use of ICT facilitates the learning process in a positive way and makes students more actively engaged in learning (Jamieson-Proctor, Albion, Finger, Cavanagh, Fitzgerald, Bond, Grimbeek, 2018) [16]. Furthermore, educators and instructional designers have been investigating what characteristics make technology an effective vehicle for education. A shift toward ideas about good education and student-centered learning activities intersects with a trend toward greater use of technology. Moreover, technology is considered as one of the essential factors in transforming developing countries for sustainable growth.

3.2.3. Collaborative Learning

Table 7 The Teaching Practices in terms of Collaborative Learning

Item Statement	Responses (N=346)					Mean	VD
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. Manages classroom structure to engage learners in meaningful exploration, discovery, and hands-on activities within a range of physical environments.	186	120	29	11	0	4.39	A
2. Uses a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills.	168	133	33	11	1	4.32	A
3. Applies a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills.	155	150	28	12	1	4.29	A
4. Establishes group goals and individual accountability.	154	145	39	7	1	4.28	A
5. Uses a range of different team-building exercises.	140	150	42	12	2	4.20	O
Overall Mean						4.30	A

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description
4.21 – 5.00	Always (A)
3.41 – 4.20	Often (O)
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes (S)
1.81 – 2.60	Rarely (R)
1.00 – 1.80	Never (N)

Table 7 displays the perceptions of the respondents as regards their teaching practices in terms of collaborative learning.

It can be noticed from the table that item “Manages classroom structure to engage learners in meaningful exploration, discovery and hands-on activities within a range of physical environment” yielded the highest computed weighted mean of 4.39 with a verbal description of “always”. Meanwhile, item “Uses a range of different team-building exercises” obtained the lowest computed weighted mean of 4.20 with a verbal description of “often”. The overall mean was recorded at 4.30 which is verbally interpreted as “always”.

These results imply that respondents actively engaged learners to process and synthesize information and concepts, rather than using rote memorization of facts and figures. Further, they allowed learners to work with each other on projects, where they must collaborate as a group to understand the concepts being presented to them.

In the same way, Huang, Su, Yang, and Liou (2017) cited that collaborative learning entails students working together without immediate teacher supervision in groups small enough that all students can participate collectively in a task [17]. Additionally, they stated that the collaborative learning approach affects students’ academic achievement positively at elementary school, middle school, high school, and university levels of education.

3.3. Teaching Performance

Evaluation of teacher performance is for the purpose of monitoring and evaluation. The data obtained from the evaluation of teacher performance could be used to make decisions on both tenured (for promotion or advancement) and untenured (for renewal, separation, or permanency) teachers. It may also provide information on the area of strengths and weaknesses of a teacher which could be used as the basis for improvement, not only for teachers but also for the school in general in terms of policy-making in teacher hiring and professional development.

3.3.1. Content Knowledge and Pedagogy

Table 8 The Teaching Performance in terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy

Item Statement	Responses (N=346)					Mean	VD
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. Applies knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas.	223	105	15	3	0	4.58	A
2. Uses a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills	187	137	18	4	0	4.47	A
3. Applies a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills.	175	145	24	2	0	4.42	A
4. Displays extensive knowledge of the important concepts in the discipline.	170	148	24	4	0	4.40	A
5. Demonstrates understanding of prerequisite relationships among topics and concepts and understands the link to necessary cognitive structures that ensure student understanding.	176	143	25	2	0	4.42	A
6. Demonstrates awareness of possible student's misconceptions and how they can be addressed.	175	148	21	2	0	4.43	A
Overall Mean						4.46	A

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description
4.21 – 5.00	Always (A)
3.41 – 4.20	Often (O)
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes (S)
1.81 – 2.60	Rarely (R)
1.00 – 1.80	Never (N)

Table 8 presents the perceptions of the respondents as regards teaching performance in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy.

Apparently, all items indicated in the table including the computed overall mean of 4.46 received the highest verbal description of “always”. A closer look at the table reveals that item “Applies knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas” obtained the highest computed weighted mean of 4.58. On the other hand, item “Displays extensive knowledge of the important concepts in the discipline” got the lowest computed weighted mean of 4.40.

These results imply that respondents strongly believed that the important skill that a teacher should process is the capacity to transform the knowledge to be taught to the students in a way that could be easily understood. Further, they knew that actual teaching should not only contain the skillful demonstration of their knowledge but should also include the ability to guide the students to understand meaningfully the content of the knowledge.

In accordance with the present findings, Graham and Fennell (2016) agreed that pedagogical content knowledge affects how teachers think about their subject matter knowledge. Moreover, they added that a skillful and very knowledgeable teacher has the potential to make the learning of mathematics more meaningful to the students. Further, they asserted that teaching or instructions without deep understanding are meaningless [18]. Effective instruction should involve pedagogical content knowledge. Pedagogical content knowledge covers conceptual and procedural knowledge and the stages of understanding that they are likely to pass through in moving from a state of having little understanding to mastery of it.

3.3.2. Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners

Table 9 The Teaching Performance in terms of Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners

Item Statement	Responses (N=346)					Mean	VD
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. Manages classroom structure to engage learners, individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery, and hands-on activities within a range of physical learning environments.	195	120	26	5	0	4.46	A
2. Manages learner behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline to ensure the learning-focused environment	176	143	23	4	0	4.42	A
3. Uses differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learners' gender, needs, strengths, interests, and experiences.	149	165	26	6	0	4.32	A
4. Understands the active nature of student learning and acquires information about levels of development for individual students.	154	154	32	6	0	4.32	A
5. Acquires knowledge from several sources about individual students' varied approaches to learning, knowledge and skills, special needs, and interests, and cultural heritages.	152	162	26	6	0	4.33	A
Overall Mean						4.37	A

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description
4.21 – 5.00	Always (A)
3.41 – 4.20	Often (O)
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes (S)
1.81 – 2.60	Rarely (R)
1.00 – 1.80	Never (N)

Table 9 reveals the perceptions of the respondents regarding teaching performance in terms of the learning environment and diversity of learners.

Interestingly, all items indicated in the table including the computed overall mean of 4.37 garnered the highest verbal interpretation of “always”. Further analysis of the table shows that item “Manages classroom structure to engage learners, individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery and hands-on activities within a range of physical learning environments” received the highest computed weighted mean of 4.46. Meanwhile, items “Uses differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learners’ gender, needs, strengths, interests, and experiences” and “Understands the active nature of student learning and acquires information about levels of development for individual students” obtained the lowest computed weighted mean of 4.32.

These results imply that respondents strongly believed that a positive classroom environment helps improve attention, reduce anxiety, and support the emotional and behavioral regulation of students. Moreover, they agreed that when they foster a positive learning culture; learners are more likely to acquire higher motivation that leads to wonderful learning outcomes.

In the same vein, Āboltiņa (2016) stated that the quality of education is significantly influenced by the modern educational environment and educational process that promotes the perception and acquisition of the content [19]. A significant role will be given to the use of modern technologies in the teaching/learning process that allows flexibility and more individual performance of tasks for the concrete learner. The implementation of the teaching/learning reform is ensured by a modern educational environment.

3.3.3. Curriculum and Planning

Table 10 The Teaching Performance in terms of Curriculum and Planning

Item Statement	Responses (N=346)					Mean	VD
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. Plans, manages, and implements developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts.	198	118	21	9	0	4.46	A
2. Participates in collegial discussions that use teacher and learner feedback to enrich teaching practice.	167	140	34	5	0	4.36	A
3. Selects, develops, organizes, and uses appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals.	144	167	26	8	1	4.29	A
4. Connects outcomes to previous and future learning.	165	150	24	7	0	4.37	A
5. Expands knowledge through professional learning groups and organizations.	147	160	31	8	0	4.29	A
6. Displays awareness of resources beyond those provided by the school.	169	143	26	8	0	4.37	A
Overall Mean						4.35	A

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description
4.21 – 5.00	Always (A)
3.41 – 4.20	Often (O)
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes (S)
1.81 – 2.60	Rarely (R)
1.00 – 1.80	Never (N)

Table 10 exhibits the perceptions of the respondents about teaching performance in terms of curriculum planning.

Noteworthy of attention is that all items indicated in the table including the computed overall mean of 4.35 registered the highest verbal description of “always”. Further observation of the table shows that the item “Plans, manages and implements developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts” received the highest computed weighted mean of 4.46. On the other hand, items “Selects, develops, organizes and uses appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals” and “Expands knowledge through professional learning groups and organizations” got the lowest computed weighted mean of 4.29.

These findings imply that respondents believed that curriculum planning develops well-coordinated, quality teaching, learning, and assessment programs that build students’ knowledge, skills, and behaviors in the disciplines, as well as their interdisciplinary and or physical, personal, and social capacities.

Accordingly, Postner and Reid (2015) reported that curriculum planning is concerned with establishing what has to be learned and how it is to be learned and how best the learning which has taken place can be evaluated. It is concerned with providing a suitable learning experience that meets the needs of the students and the aims of the course. Further, they suggested that the key to curriculum planning is to forge an educationally sound and logical link between planned intentions (expressed as objective), course content teaching and learning methods, and the assessment of student learning while taking account of student characteristics [20].

3.3.4. Assessment and Reporting

Table 11 The Teaching Performance in terms of Assessment and Reporting

Item Statement	Responses (N=346)					Mean	VD
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. Designs, selects, organizes, and uses diagnostic, formative, and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements.	206	111	25	4	0	4.50	A
2. Designs authentic assessment, with real-world applications as appropriate.	130	168	41	7	0	4.22	A
3. Develop rubrics according to specified learning objectives.	169	143	30	4	0	4.38	A
4. Monitors and evaluates learner progress and achievement using learner attainment data.	205	112	24	5	0	4.49	A
5. Communicates promptly and clearly the learners' needs, progress and achievement to key stakeholders, including parents/ guardians.	205	111	23	7	0	4.49	A
Overall Mean						4.42	A

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description
4.21 – 5.00	Always (A)
3.41 – 4.20	Often (O)
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes (S)
1.81 – 2.60	Rarely (R)
1.00 – 1.80	Never (N)

Table 11 reveals the perceptions of the respondents as regards teaching performance in terms of assessment and reporting.

Apparently, all items indicated in the table including the computed overall mean of 4.42 yielded the highest verbal description of “always”. Further examination of the table shows that item “Designs, selects, organizes and uses diagnostic, formative and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements” registered the highest computed weighted mean of 4.50. On the other hand, item “Designs authentic assessment, with real-world applications as appropriate” got the lowest computed weighted mean of 4.22.

These findings imply that respondents were highly aware that teaching, learning, assessment, and reporting are all connected. Moreover, they knew that planning for assessment and reporting is an important part of planning for teaching and learning. It is important, then, to consider ways of bringing planning for assessment and reporting into subject and lesson planning.

In the same vein, Blivenfield (2018) asserted that assessment, evaluation, and reporting are used throughout the teaching-learning cycle in order to compile clear, accurate, and timely information on student progress and proficiency. Moreover, he reiterated that assessment and reporting enable teachers to determine how activities and strategies are working and if any changes are required in programming to assist children to achieve the learning expectations for students [21].

3.4. The Learning Outcomes of the Students

It can be seen from the table that more than one-half or 50.87 percent of the teacher respondents' students registered grades that ranged from 85 to 89 with a verbal description of “very satisfactory”. Meanwhile, more than two-fifths or 41.62 percent obtained grades that ranged from 80 to 84 with a verbal interpretation of “satisfactory”. On the other hand, 7.51 percent garnered grades that ranged from 90 to 100 with a verbal interpretation of “outstanding”. A closer look at the table shows that the grades of the students ranged from 82 to 99 with a mean of 85.52 (very satisfactory) and a standard deviation of 2.69. These results indicated that approximately, 235 students registered grades that ranged from 82.83 to 88.21.

These findings imply that students had grades that indicate a good grasp of the subject matter or an excellent grasp in one area balanced with a satisfactory grasp in the other area.

A paper by Brookhart, Guskey, Bowers, McMillan, Smith, Smith, Stevens, Welsh (2016) claiming that early 20th century studies generally revealed that most of the students obtained a very satisfactory academic performance. Furthering their findings by stating: “recent studies of the relationships of grades to tested achievement and survey studies of teachers” grading practices and beliefs suggest that grades assess a multidimensional construct containing both cognitive and non-cognitive factors reflecting what teachers’ value in student work [22].”

Table 12 Descriptive Measures of the Learning Outcomes of the Students

Grade	F (N=346)	Percent	Verbal Description
90 – 100	26	7.51	Outstanding (O)
85 – 89	176	50.87	Very Satisfactory (VS)
80 – 84	144	41.62	Satisfactory (S)
75 – 79	0	0.00	Fairly Satisfactory (FS)
74 and below	0	0.00	Did not meet Expectation (DE)
Range	82 – 99		
Mean	85.52		
Verbal Description	Very Satisfactory (VS)		
Standard Deviation	2.69		

3.5. The Relationship between Instructional Supervision and Teaching Practices, Teaching Performance and Learning Outcomes

Table 13 Results of the Correlation Analysis between Instructional Supervision and Teaching Practices, Teaching Performance and Learning Outcomes

Item	Instructional Supervision		
	r-value	p-value	Significance
Teaching Practices	0.638	0.000	Highly Significant
Teaching Performance	0.619	0.000	Highly Significant
Learning Outcomes	0.617	0.000	Highly Significant

Legend: $p < 0.01$ - Highly Significant

Results of the analyses showed that a highly significant relationship existed between instructional supervision and teaching practices. This highly significant correlation was brought about by the fact that the computed probability value of 0.000 is less than the 0.01 level of significance. Moreover, a direct correlation was found between these variables as manifested by the positive sign of the computed r-value of 0.638. This discloses that as the level of instructional supervision increases the level of teaching practices also increases.

Similarly, a highly significant relationship was found between instructional supervision and teaching performance as implied by the computed probability value of 0.000 which is less than the 0.01 significance level. Furthermore, a direct correlation existed between these variables as indicated by the positive sign of the computed r-value of 0.619. This means that as the level of instructional supervision increases the level of teaching performance also increases.

Similarly, a highly significant relationship was found between instructional supervision and students’ learning outcomes as indicated by the computed probability value of 0.000 which is less than the 0.01 level of significance. Moreover, a direct correlation existed between these variables as manifested by the positive sign of the computed r-value of 0.617. This indicates that as the level of instructional supervision increases the level of students’ learning outcomes also increases.

These findings imply that instructional supervision greatly influenced the teaching practices and teaching performance of the teachers as well as the learning outcomes of the students. Additionally, this indicates that instructional supervision significantly explains teacher effectiveness in the classroom which has been proven to improve student learning.

The findings of this study were in line with the results of other researches in this field. Sule, Ameh, and Egbai (2015) for instance, studied the relationship between instructional supervision and the roles teachers play in ensuring effectiveness in secondary schools [23]. Their study revealed that classroom observations positively contributed to teacher effectiveness in a school. Similarly, Veloo, Komujji, and Khalid (2015) in their study about the effect of clinical supervision on the teaching performance of secondary school teachers, relatedly established that formal observations significantly contributed to improved teacher preparation, lesson development, learner assessment, and classroom control [24]. However, several pieces of literature (e.g. Tesfaw & Hofman, 2016; Milanowski, 2017; Holland, 2018) argue that formal classroom observations have little effect on teaching practices. These scholars meanwhile advocate for more frequent, short, unannounced, informal classroom observations by school authorities to motivate teachers to adopt effective pedagogical practices. They contend that informal classroom observations provide a better picture of the teacher's competence and his or her pedagogical practices than formal observations. Additionally, these scholars advised that for better results, the frequency and purpose of the walk-throughs or short visits to classrooms should be collaboratively established by the teacher and administrator [25] [26] [27].

Results of the conducted interview conform to the above findings. When the teacher respondents were asked "Does instructional supervision affect your teaching practices, performance, and the learning outcomes? In what way?" These respondents replied that through instructional supervision they became aware and informed of their strengths that they need to sustain and weaknesses that they need to improve. By improving their teaching strategies, the level of their teaching performance will increase and as final results, the level of the students' academic performance will also increase.

4. Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

- There is a significant relationship between instructional supervision and teaching practices.
- There is a significant relationship between instructional supervision and teaching performance.
- There is a significant relationship between instructional supervision and learning outcomes.
- The instructional supervision greatly influenced the teaching practices, teaching performance, and learning outcomes.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of Conflict of interest

I declare no conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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